

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report of activities and second update of the
Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
Deliverable D6.3**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.3

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results

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Abbreviation list

Acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
EW3	ESiWACE3
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High Performance Computing
IPM	Innovation Project Manager
IPMP	Intellectual Property Management Plan
ITC	Inclusiveness Target Countries
METH	Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
PMO	Project Manager Office
PROD	Product (new or improved)
SCI	Scientific discovery, model, theory (...)
SW	Software
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels

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1. Abstract/publishable summary

This document comprises the second updated version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) for the ESiWACE3 project set out in ESiWACE3 Deliverable 6.1 dated 30/06/2023 and updated in Deliverable 6.2 dated 28/06/2024. It describes the goals and target audiences for communication and dissemination of the project’s outcomes, the channels to be used and the actions to be taken. The document also reports on actions already taken in line with the CDEP since Deliverable 6.2 was submitted.

2. Conclusion & Results

The updated CDEP is set out in section 4, which also lists actions taken to date. A final report and update of the plan is envisaged for month 48 of the project.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the GA:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
O4. Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	Yes
O5. Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
O6. Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth System science and HPC, and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Serve as a landing point for the European community of Earth System modellers to cooperate and exchange knowledge and expertise.	Yes
Strong focus on communication and networking activities to broaden the community.	Yes
Particularly addressing early career scientists and female researchers and contacting Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs).	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) provides the context, strategy and intended actions to be taken to facilitate engagement of the project with its target audiences and to ensure that the outcomes of the project are disseminated to those who can benefit from them. It sets out the goals for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, identifies the various audiences and describes the channels that will be used to reach them.

Specifically, the CDEP identifies concrete actions to:

- raise awareness of the project, its objectives, progress and outcomes with interested parties beyond the project's community;
- seek interaction and engagement with selected audiences;
- promote the services, training and tools developed within the project to potential users;
- disseminate the results of research conducted within the project to the wider weather and climate modelling and HPC communities;
- identify the potential for exploitation of the results of the project.

As at the time of writing, month 36 of the project, naturally, many of the planned activities have already been undertaken. These are also described in this report.

4.2. Objectives

The purpose of the CDEP is to define the strategy for building a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth System modelling across Earth System science and HPC and for establishing connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives. Building a well-connected community is essential to ensure knowledge transfer and exchange across the many actors in Earth System science and HPC, including domain scientists, technology providers, and end users.

Through its CDEP, ESiWACE3 aims to increase its outreach while achieving a more inclusive and diverse community. This includes creating a network of ITCs, by identifying and contacting relevant actors in these countries and sharing technical and communication expertise. The strategy also promotes gender equity by engaging in ongoing activities addressed to women in HPC and empowering female Early Career Scientists (ECSs).

The coordination and support to the ESiWACE3 community is based on three main concepts:

- sustaining and growing the network established in previous ESiWACE phases by providing new opportunities and means for fruitful interactions;
- anchoring the ESiWACE network to ongoing activities to connect the engaged community with other networks (European initiatives, CASTIEL2, CoEs, NCCs, ...);
- promoting training and capacity-building activities across the community.

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The ultimate goal is to promote an active, inclusive, and sustained community, foster the uptake of the project outcomes, and maximise the long-term impact and sustainability of the project and its results.

4.3. Target audiences

In the period since the first version of the CDEP was produced, the main target audiences for ESiWACE3 communications activities have been kept under review. The following broad categories, identified in the stakeholder mapping exercise, undertaken as Milestone M6.1 and extended by one item in D6.2 remain unchanged:

- scientific community (Earth System modellers)
- HPC community
- training participants
- HPC industry (HPC technologists, technology providers, high-capacity data experts...)
- EuroHPC/EC ecosystem (European digital agenda-related initiatives, CASTIEL2, CoEs, NCCs, ...)
- public authorities such as national meteorological agencies and authorities responsible for climate adaptation
- specialised media

The mapping itself, as reported in D6.2, is shown in Figure 1 for reference.

Figure 1. Mapping of current and potential stakeholders.

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Interviews have also been conducted with representatives of some of these groups, especially the audiences for training and software services, to better understand their needs. The insights gained from these discussions have been taken into consideration in planning communication about ongoing ESiWACE3 training and services opportunities.

4.4. Planned and completed actions

Communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation are crucial to maximise the project's scientific, economic, and societal impact. The purpose of the activities conducted within this framework is to enhance the visibility of the goals and outcomes of the project and increase awareness of how a new generation of weather and climate models that allow realistic simulations of the Earth System can improve our understanding of weather risks in a changing climate. All project partners contribute to these activities, monitored through target indicators, followed up and updated to maximise their impact.

Communication and dissemination activities and materials are crucial to support the ESiWACE3 project community engagement and to reach all relevant target audiences. Table 1 (from the GA) lists the community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities envisaged in ESiWACE3. Some modifications (already included in D6.2) have been made subsequently to the detailed plans as a result of learning from other projects and from consultation with the different audiences, but overall, the intended activities remain unchanged.

Table 1. Outline of community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination activities envisaged in the Grant Agreement.

Table 4: List of community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities planned in ESiWACE3

Type	Activity (target group)	Description and purpose (target indicator)
C	Project website (all)	Maintain and update the existing ESiWACE website, the project's main communication hub, aimed at those involved or interested in the project. It provides the project description, latest news, events, reports, press releases, public deliverables, publications and all the communication materials (>400 visits)
C	Social media (all)	Regular posts will be made to reach a wider community, raise awareness and increase project visibility. We will build on ESiWACE social media accounts (Twitter and YouTube) (>700 followers on Twitter)
C	Communication kit (all)	Set of communication materials, including a brochure, presentation and poster templates, roll-up, and a presentation video (>250 video views)
C	Newsletters (all)	Quarterly project newsletters will be distributed to communicate about the project to the community of interest (people subscribed to the ESiWACE mailing list) (>350 subscribers reached)
C	Press releases (journalists, all)	Press/media releases and briefing materials aimed to generate interest in the project, communicate about events and disseminate results at a local and EU level (2 press releases)
C/D	Videos (all)	The project will produce different types of videos that will help communicate the project objectives, status, and results obtained to various audiences. These may include science explainers, project scientists' biographies, and videos documenting project events. Videos with a selection of the new services developed in WP4 will be created (>200 views/video)
CE	Clustering activities (scientific community, European Digital Agenda, EuroHPC ecosystem)	The project will cluster with other projects and initiatives relevant to HPC for Earth system modelling, such as Destination Earth, other EuroHPC funded COE's and related CSA activities, the ENES ¹⁰ network and national and international projects including NextGEMS, Warm World, ACROSS, MAELSTROM and EXCLAIM (>5 participated activities)
D	Scientific publications (scientific community)	Public project reports and publications in peer-reviewed journals will disseminate key project findings to academic audiences (>20 publications)

Type	Activity (target group)	Description and purpose (target indicator)
	EuroHPC ecosystem)	
CE	Organisation of ENES HPC conference (scientific community, EuroHPC ecosystem)	The organisation of two joint ENES HPC workshop editions (2024 and 2026) will allow a deeper engagement with the project's community of interest (>50 participants/conference)
CE	Activities to reach ITCs, women and ECSs (specific networks)	Individuals and institutions from ITCs will be engaged by sharing technical and communication expertise (>= 5 established contacts) Gender equity will be promoted in the events organised by the project (>20% female participation) Engagement with Early-Career Scientists (ECSs) will give particular attention in the events organised by the project (>40% ECS participation)
D	Slide decks and factsheets (scientific community, HPC technology providers)	Slide decks and factsheets to help disseminate the catalogue of new services created in ESiWACE3 or any other relevant project outcome (>4 services showcased)
CE	Hackathons (scientific community)	Four hackathons to provide hands-on training on ESiWACE3 developments, support the exploitation and sustainability of ESiWACE3 services, and enhance the collaboration within the European modelling community (>80 participants)
CE	Summer schools (ECSs)	Two summer schools targeted at early career scientists to train a new generation of weather and climate modellers to effectively use the latest HPC environments (>60 ECSs)
D	Training materials (scientific community, ECSs)	Teaching material to transfer knowledge on specific project-related topics that will be published online and advertised in relevant platforms to reach a wide audience (>50 downloads)

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4.4.1. Communication (Task 6.1)

The communication actions aim to reach the project target groups and increase the project's visibility. Several communication tools and channels are used to inform target audiences at a local, national, and EU level about the project goals and key messages and maximise the impact of the project communication. These tools and channels include (among others): a revision and update of the existing ESiWACE visual identity; the maintenance, revision, update, and curation of new content of the established [ESiWACE website](#); the social media channels (X (former [Twitter](#)), new [BlueSky](#) account, [LinkedIn](#) and [YouTube](#)); new communication material (communication kit, videos, infographics, roll-up, etc.); press releases; and quarterly ESiWACE newsletters. Communication materials are made available on the project website and advertised on social media channels.

A range of activities have already been completed, and those are reported here. Forthcoming communication activities and their impact will be reported in the final update and report on the CDEP, in deliverable 6.4. The effectiveness of different communication channels in reaching the target audiences is kept under review, for example, by polling participants in training events and workshops about how they became aware of the activities. At the time of writing (month 36), the LinkedIn account has 548 followers, the X (Twitter) account 542 followers, the BlueSky account 245 followers and the YouTube channel 201 subscribers.

Table 2 shows the actions already undertaken and those further actions planned to support the communication of the project. Actions already taken and reported in the first version of the CDEP submitted in Deliverables 6.1 and 6.2, i.e., up to month 18 of the project, are shown in grey.

Table 2. Communication actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Visual identity	Visual identity reviewed: new logo and colour palette created.	-
Communication kit	<p>Templates updated in line with the new visual identity.</p> <p>A range of infographics produced to illustrate the project objectives, services catalogue and training opportunities.</p> <p>Creation of further new material, such as dynamic presentation material that can be displayed on conference stands.</p> <p>Creation of a leaflet and some stickers to promote the project.</p>	Creation of more leaflets for EMS-HPC events such as ISC26, EGU26, EuroHPC Summit and the 9th ENES HPC Workshop.
Project website	<p>Static website content reviewed and updated to present the new phase of the project.</p> <p>Content updated and augmented regularly.</p> <p>Comprehensive modernisation and complete redesign and rebuild of the website to better present and explain the project and its services.</p>	Continue completing the new website with the results and success stories recollected at the end of the project.

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	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Social media	<p>Existing social media channels from previous phases of the project (Twitter and YouTube) taken over.</p> <p>"#MeetESiWACE3Partners" campaign presenting the partners of the ESiWACE3 Consortium</p> <p>New social media channel opened on LinkedIn and BlueSky.</p> <p>Content posted regularly to publicise training opportunities, services calls, and project updates.</p>	Continue to post content.
Newsletter	Template for the newsletter updated and 10 issues released (every three months).	Release of further quarterly issues.
Videos	<p>Eight videos presenting the project released on the website.</p> <p>Six videos presenting ESiWACE2 services created, released on the website and YouTube channel, and promoted on the social media channels.</p> <p>Creation of an animated video to present and better explain the main objectives of the project.</p> <p>A video presenting the service 2 call.</p> <p>Seven mid-term project videos presenting the work achieved at the middle of the project per WP and the Data-compression lab.</p> <p>Further videos created to present ESiWACE3 services projects, hackathons, summer schools, and scientist bios.</p>	<p>Six videos concluding the work of each WP at the end of the project.</p> <p>A wrap up video to finalize the project.</p>
Press releases	-	Press releases to be issued once newsworthy results are available.

4.4.2. Engagement (Tasks 6.2 & 6.3)

Building a well-connected community is essential to ensure knowledge transfer and exchange across the many actors in Earth System science and HPC, including domain scientists, technology providers, and end users. The ESiWACE3 engagement strategy includes creating a network of Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs), promoting gender equity by engaging in ongoing activities addressed to women in HPC, attracting, retaining, and advancing more high-quality female scientific researchers and empowering female Early Career Scientists (ECSS). The aim is to enhance the ESiWACE3 community engagement, mainly focusing

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on increasing its outreach while achieving a more active, inclusive, gender-balanced, diverse, and sustained community.

Clustering with other European projects and initiatives, in particular through engagement in the activities and networks promoted by CASTIEL2 and potential follow-up projects once CASTIEL2 ends, will also be fostered. Such interactions will ensure links with the European ecosystem of HPC stakeholders and initiatives related to the European digital agenda. The objective is to raise awareness of the project topics and results of interest for the community. Specific actions include the organisation of the joint ENES HPC Workshop editions for 2024 and 2026, the coordination of project requests of HPC resources through the EuroHPC CoE call and the participation of ESiWACE3 in conferences, workshops and events (such as the EGU, ISC, SC, etc.). Information on the participation of ESiWACE3 in such events is collected in an Excel document accessible from the project's wiki.

In coordination with WP5, videos documenting the training events organised by the project (hackathons, summer schools, etc.) are also being developed and disseminated within the ITCs network. Gender balance amongst presenters and participation of female ECSs is regularly considered when promoting the project's events and accepting participants. To facilitate and promote this, a guide regarding the organisation of inclusive events was developed and [released](#).

Table 3 shows the actions already undertaken and those planned to support the engagement of target communities in the project. Actions already taken and reported in the first version of the CDEP submitted in Deliverable 6.1 and D6.2, i.e., up to month 18 of the project, are shown in grey.

Table 3. Engagement actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

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	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Community mailing list	<p>Ongoing management of the community mailing list.</p> <p>Communications circulated to the list regularly.</p>	Further communications issued
Mapping of potential stakeholders	<p>Interviews with relevant participants in ESiWACE3 and the earlier project phases.</p> <p>Surveys of the ESiWACE community (contacts from project mailing lists and social media channels).</p> <p>Interviews with contacts in related projects such as IS-ENES3.</p> <p>Direct approaches to NCC contacts made through the CASTIEL network.</p> <p>Interviews with contacts from partners' professional networks.</p> <p>Trawls of modelling groups through the CORDEX network.</p>	Ongoing follow-up of contacts formed through participation in conferences and other projects.
Participation in conferences/workshops/events	<p>Coordination of ESiWACE3 participation in annual/biennial events including EuroHPC Summits, European Geosciences Union (EGU) GAs, ISC, Supercomputing, HiPEAC, etc.</p> <p>Participation in scientific workshops run by the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR).</p>	<p>Coordination of participation in future events, presenting our work on oral or poster presentations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -HiPEAC26 -EGU26 -ISC26 -EuroHPC Summit <p>Preparation of additional display materials to attract audiences, including dynamic poster displays and videos.</p>
Clustering with other EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs and related initiatives	<p>ESiWACE3 is active in various CASTIEL2-coordinated advisory and technical groups, including the Project Management Technical Group, the HPC CoE Council, training, communication, legacy software and CI/CD taskforces.</p> <p>ESiWACE3 partners also contributed legal support to CASTIEL2, and contribute to the C2ISS and the EuroCC Access portal.</p> <p>Online training event to held in collaboration with NCC Austria in September 2024 and January 2025.</p> <p>ESiWACE3 co-organised a conference workshop at PPAM24 with CoEs HiDALGO2, Plasma-PEPSC, BioEXCEL-3, EXCELLERAT, EoCoE and the HANAMI project.</p> <p>ESiWACE3 has organised a joint CoE workshop for women in HPC at HiPEAC 2025 in collaboration with MAX, MultiXScale, ChEESE, and POP3.</p>	Further collaborative training events, hackathons, workshops, webinars, etc.

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	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Clustering with other projects and initiatives relevant to HPC for earth system modelling	<p>Preparation of the first and second ESiWACE3 summer school, organised in collaboration with the WarmWorld project in Aug/Sep 24 and Aug 25 respectively.</p> <p>Involvement in the #ClimateResearchNet network for communication for European climate research projects.</p> <p>I invited representatives of OptimESM, EERIE and Destination Earth to participate in the 3rd General Assembly in November 2024 in Hamburg (Germany).</p>	<p>.</p> <p>Further collaborative training events, hackathons, workshops, webinars, etc.</p>
Hackathons and summer schools	<p>First hackathon held in Espoo, Finland in October 2023.</p> <p>Second hackathon held in Amsterdam, Netherlands in June 2024.</p> <p>First ESiWACE3 summer school to held in Espoo, Finland in Aug/Sep 24.</p> <p>Second Summer school held in Geesthacht (Germany) in August 2025</p>	<p>Two further hackathons are being prepared in April and October 2025.</p>
ITCs, women and ECRs	<p>Updating the mapping of potential stakeholders undertaken for M6.1.</p> <p>Mapping of modelling teams in ITCs through contacts with NCCs in ITCs.</p> <p>Participation in the 4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing conference in Riga, Latvia.</p> <p>LinkedIn campaign highlighting ESiWACE3's female researchers for International Women's Day.</p> <p>Compilation of best-practice guidance for ensuring a diversity-friendly atmosphere at training events and workshops</p>	<p>Further training events offered online to facilitate participation by researchers from ITCs.</p> <p>Increased engagement with climate research networks active in the ITCs, such as the Pannonian Basin Experiment (PANNEX).</p> <p>Increased engagement with ECR networks such as the Young Earth Systems Scientists (YESS) community.</p>
ENES HPC workshops	<p>ENES HPC workshop held in Lecce, Italy in May 2024, and associated communication and promotion activities.</p>	<p>Organisation of the next ENES HPC workshop in 2026.</p>
Requests for HPC resources	<p>Coordination of project requests for HPC resources through the EuroHPC calls.</p>	<p>Further coordination of requests through EuroHPC calls.</p>
Interaction with HPC technology providers	<p>Participation in ISC, SuperComputing, HPCKP Annual Meeting, etc.</p>	<p>Further participation in future international and national HPC meetings.</p>

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4.4.3. Dissemination (Task 6.4)

The primary purpose of the project's dissemination activities is to promote the project results and services and their uptake by different communities by delivering relevant and tailored information to the various target audiences in a form that is easy for them to access.

To facilitate dissemination, ESiWACE3 complies with the Open Science policy required by the "Horizon Europe" programme. This policy states mandatory open access to publications, and open science principles are applied throughout the programme. Within this framework, ESiWACE3 is committed to expanding and sustaining the ESiWACE Zenodo Community by adding new open-access publications created within the project. Scientific results are published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at relevant scientific conferences and events. All dissemination materials will be shared through the project communication channels. When relevant, they will be shared at project-related or project-relevant events. ESiWACE3 will also liaise with partner NCCs to make links to training materials available on their websites.

An important element of the project dissemination strategy relies on video materials. First, a series of videos has been produced to help present the project and communicate its objectives and goals. Another set of videos incorporates successful user stories to showcase the services developed in previous phases of ESiWACE. In 2025 we produced a short (3,5 Minutes) animation video (ESiWACE - Towards exascale weather and climate simulations) and further videos with a selection of new services developed by WP4 to support the preparation of the project's new catalogue of services. The 9th ENES HPC Workshop will be documented with videos and testimonia from attendees. The video strategy will be accordingly adjusted as the project necessities evolve. All videos are available on the project's YouTube channel.

Moreover, slide decks were developed to disseminate further the new services catalogue and other dissemination materials (such as leaflets and factsheets) showcasing the different services or any other relevant project outcome. The compilation of this material, together with the series of videos, creates a dynamic portfolio of the services created in ESiWACE3.

Table 4 shows the actions already undertaken and those planned to support dissemination of research outcomes and materials from ESiWACE3. Actions already taken and reported in the first version of the CDEP submitted in Deliverable 6.1, i.e., up to month 6 of the project, are shown in grey.

Table 4. Dissemination actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

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	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Videos	<p>Videos presenting the project and its aims.</p> <p>Videos showcasing services delivered in previous phases of the project.</p> <p>Production of an animated video describing the project for display at conferences, for example.</p> <p>Production of Videos to highlight the portfolio of new services offered in ESiWACE3.</p> <p>Production of videos explaining the progress of the WPs at mid-project</p> <p>Video explaining the Data Compression lab</p>	<p>Further videos documenting activities such as the 9th ENES HPC Workshop</p> <p>Videos concluding the WPs objectives and summarize of the project.</p> <p>Wrap up video of ESiWACE3 at the end of the project.</p>
Zenodo community	<p>Take over and update the visual identity of the existing ESiWACE Zenodo community.</p> <p>Ongoing addition of open access publications to the community.</p>	<p>Further open access publications and training materials added to the community.</p>
Scientific publications	<p>7 Publications of ESiWACE3 results in peer-reviewed journals, 6 of them open-access journals.</p> <p>Dissemination of results through non-peer-reviewed industry channels such as insidehpc.com.</p>	<p>Further articles in peer-reviewed and other journals.</p>
Services catalogue	<p>Catalogue of topics that might be offered as software services drawn up and issued (D4.1).</p> <p>Infographic promoting the catalogue produced and distributed on the project website and by social media channels.</p> <p>Further refinement of the description of the catalogue on the (new) project website to clarify the offering.</p>	
Software support	<p>Website announcement and promotion on social media of the first call for proposals for software support.</p> <p>Website announcements and promotion on social media of two further calls for proposals. The second of these focuses on support to use tools developed by ESiWACE3 partners.</p> <p>Videos depicting success stories from software support offered in ESiWACE2.</p> <p>Promotion of the lastcall for proposals.</p> <p>Success stories leaflets and banners reporting on the outcomes of ESiWACE3 software support services.</p>	<p>Final preparation of more success stories to deliver to CASTIEL 2 and display on the website of the project.</p>
Training events and materials	<p>Publication on the ESiWACE3 website of the project training events calendar.</p>	

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	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
	Ongoing publication of relevant events on the training events calendar. Dissemination of workshop training materials through the Zenodo community and through GitHub Publication of ESiWACE3 training materials on the project website. .	Addition of further materials to Zenodo and GitHub.

4.4.4. Exploitation (Task 6.5)

To ensure that the full scientific and societal benefits of the project are realised, the outputs that result from it need to be made openly available and accessible for further research and development by the wider scientific and HPC community and not just by the project partners. But in doing so, intellectual property and related rights issues must be handled correctly. To provide a framework for the exploitation of project results and to ensure that proper knowledge management procedures are followed, an Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP) has been drawn up. An updated version for month 36 of the project is set out in Appendix 1.

The IPMP provides guidance on the legal framework within which the project's knowledge management takes place. It sets out the respective responsibilities for exploitation within the project, and details the procedures for the identification of exploitable results by partners and their categorisation according to their potential to be exploited.

Templates for collecting information about results and about any knowledge protection measures planned have been made available to project partners, and will assist them in meeting their obligation to exploit their results during the period for four years after the project has ended.

A range of measures will be adopted by the project to make results available for exploitation, including peer-reviewed publications in scientific journals, dissemination of code and publication of research datasets. A particular focus continues to be sustaining, further developing and expanding the services developed as prototypes in ESiWACE2, and disseminating them to the wider community.

Table 5 shows the actions already undertaken and those planned to support ESiWACE3 exploitation.

Table 5. Exploitation actions already undertaken and those planned for the coming months.

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	Actions already undertaken	Future actions planned
Context and legal framework	Defined	
Exploitation guidelines	Defined	
IP Portfolio	Development of supporting tailored material (templates). When necessary, meetings with partners to explain implementation and templates Identification of results and elaboration of the preliminary IP Portfolio. Update of IP portfolio after month 36	Follow up of results, updated of the IP portfolio, if needed, and KERs identification
Exploitation	Identification of preliminary exploitation paths. Two Exploitation Workshops for discussing appropriate exploitation paths and potential actions to maximise impact.	Final Exploitation Workshop for discussing appropriate exploitation paths and potential actions to maximise impact at the final general assembly.
IP traceability	Under evaluation.	Continuous monitoring.

4.5. Feedback

The effectiveness of the different communications activities described in this plan will be monitored by seeking feedback from participants in training events and workshops, as well as applicants for software support services. Statistics for engagement with the social media channels are also monitored on an ongoing basis. Download statistics for online training materials will be monitored once these materials are live.

5. References

- [Grant agreement](#)
- [Horizon Europe](#)
- [Horizon Europe, open science](#)
- [ESiWACE3 M6.1](#) (2023) Network mapping and engagement strategy
- [ESiWACE3 D6.1](#) (2023) Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (CDEP)
- [ESiWACE3 D6.2](#) (2024) Report of activities and first update of the Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan
- [ESiWACE3 M5.1](#) (2023) Training event calendar
- [ESiWACE3 M4.1](#) (2023) First call for projects in Service 1
- [ESiWACE3 M4.2](#) (2024) First call for projects in Service 2
- [ESiWACE3 M5.2](#) (2023) Report of first hackathon
- [ESiWACE3 D5.4](#) (2025) Report on training materials
- [ESiWACE3 D4.1](#) (2023) Initial release of catalogue of expertise and potential service offer
- [ESiWACE3 D7.5](#) (2023) Collaboration plan

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- [ESiWACE3 D7.6](#) (2024) First update of Collaboration plan
- ESiWACE3 D7.7 (2025) Second update of Collaboration plan
- [Promoting inclusiveness in ESiWACE3 training and events \(2025\)](#)

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

A major development since the preparation of the first ESiWACE3 CDEP in D6.1 has been the expansion of CASTIEL2's activities in support of coordination of the work of the EuroHPC JU-funded centres of excellence (CoEs). ESiWACE3 is active in several CASTIEL2-organised groups, as well as in the co-organisation with other CoEs of events such as the workshop at the International Conference on Parallel Processing and Applied Mathematics (PPAM24) in September 2024.

At the same time, it is increasingly clear that ESiWACE3 will need to continue to focus effort and resources on domain-specific networks and contacts, to ensure that the training and services that it offers meet the needs of its core audience in the climate and weather modelling community. To be relevant to the target community, the tools and training developed by ESiWACE3 need to reflect the particular context, architecture and requirements of weather and climate modelling, and thus will not all be readily transferable to the audiences for other CoEs or the wider EuroHPC community.

One emerging challenge for the project's aim to promote engagement and participation amongst researchers in the ITCs is in ensuring the accessibility of training to all. The in-person training events - hackathons and summer schools - envisaged in the project proposal were expected to be hosted by ESiWACE3 project partners. But a consequence of this is that they would take place at locations that are geographically remote from the ITC audiences we aim to reach, and feedback has been received that suggests that travel costs are one barrier to participation by ITC (and ECR) researchers. Consideration is therefore being given to options for improving the attractiveness and accessibility of future ESiWACE3 training to these target audiences.

Also, due to a noticeable decline in engagement and followers on Twitter/X—likely stemming from changes in the platform's management and reduced user activity—we diversified our communication strategy by launching a Bluesky account. While Bluesky has not yet gained substantial traction, LinkedIn has proven to be a highly effective channel. Our presence there has grown steadily, with a marked increase in followers and engagement. In particular, the decision to publish the ESiWACE3 newsletter through LinkedIn's integrated newsletter tool has significantly expanded our reach, surpassing the performance of our traditional email newsletter and becoming a key outlet for audience outreach. These strategic shifts have helped maintain strong communication with the community without impacting the project's timeline or resource allocation.

The exploitation section of the CDEP has been much expanded with the incorporation of a separate ESiWACE3 Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP) and report on initial activities. These provide the framework for ensuring the effective exploitation of outcomes from the project as these take shape.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

This deliverable, and the updated CDEP and IPMO that it contains, provide the framework for the dissemination and exploitation of the results and outcomes of ESiWACE3 to the various earth system modelling and HPC communities who can make use of them and build on them in their own development work. It also covers a range of activities aimed at reinforcing the European modelling and HPC communities through strengthened links with other projects and ongoing initiatives at European and national level, such as other EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs, CASTIEL2, the ENES network and model development projects, and is complementary to the ESiWACE3 collaboration plan (ESiWACE3 Deliverable 7.5).

8. Sustainability

Ensuring the sustainability of the results produced during the ESiWACE3 project - and in earlier phases of the project - is the ultimate objective of WP6. This is the goal of the exploitation measures described in sub-section 4.4.4, and it also underpins the communication and dissemination activities.

In working towards the objective, WP6 collaborates closely with other ESiWACE3 work packages. It gives visibility to the software services provided through WP4 which promote the uptake and ongoing use of the tools and methods developed in ESiWACE. It also raises awareness of the training opportunities offered by WP5, which aim to disseminate knowledge and contribute to skills development amongst the target audiences, thus leading to a strengthened and sustainable weather and climate modelling community.

To this end, two workshops about exploitation, sustainability, and impact have been held, as stated in the GA. The first one will take place during the 3rd ESiWACE3 General Assembly in Hamburg in November 2024. The second exploitation workshop was held as virtual meeting during the virtual 4th General Assembly in November 2025. During these events, the partners, through a collective brainstorming exercise led by the exploitation and impact officer, elaborated on potential routes to sustain the exploitation of the CoE and its results during and after the end of the project itself.

The measures described in this deliverable also contribute to a strengthening of the HPC community more generally, through the collaboration and pursuit of synergies with partner projects and initiatives that they involve.

9. Community engagement, dissemination and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)

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	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)
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Dissemination of the deliverable will be achieved through:

- Publication on the [project website](#);
- Depositing it in the [ESiWACE Zenodo community](#).

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Table 6. Dissemination and engagement activities.

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of people reached
Presentation	PASC	26-28/06/2023 Davos (Switzerland)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/10599997	30
Presentation	NOAA UIFCW	24-28/07/2023 Boulder (USA)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/8366985	30
Workshop	NCAR	09-10/11/2023 Boulder (USA)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10580106 https://zenodo.org/records/10580083	80
Workshop	RSE conference	05/09/2023 Swansea (UK)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10598353	25
Workshop	SuperComputing23	12-17/11/2023 Denver (USA)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/10581020	40-50
Display of video	SuperComputing23	12-17/11/2023 Denver (USA)	HPC community	N/A	200
Presentation	Bits&Chips event	10/12/2023 Eindhoven (Netherlands)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10598076	40
Workshop	HiPEAC 2024	17-19/01/2024 Munich (Germany)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/10580122	15
Participation in outreach event	EU Digital Ambassadors	06/03/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	Government representatives and policymakers	https://zenodo.org/records/12634540	10
Poster	EuroHPC Summit	19/03/2024 Antwerp (Belgium)	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12570925	750

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Presentation	EuroHPC Summit	21/03/2024 Antwerp (Belgium)	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12570886	750
Training event	FDO Summit training day	19/03/2024 Berlin (Germany)	Scientific community	N/A	40
Presentation	FDO Summit	20-21/03/2024 Berlin (Germany)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10960301	150
Presentation	To NCC Netherlands and NCC Italy	02/04/2024 Virtual	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12634662	10
Participation in panel discussion	Ocean Decade Conference	08/04/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10953215	30
Display of video	Ocean Decade Conference	10-12/04/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/10953215	250
Display of video	4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing Conference	11-12/04/2024 Riga (Latvia)	HPC community	N/A	300
Presentation	4th Baltic HPC and Cloud Computing Conference	11-12/04/2024 Riga (Latvia)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12633828	300
Presentation	EGU 2024	14-19/04/2024 Vienna (Austria)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/11060523	40
Poster	EGU 2024	14-19/04/2024 Vienna (Austria)	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/records/12570826	100
Presentation	HPCKP annual meeting	08-09/05/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12634440	50
Poster	ISC 2024	12-16/05/2024 Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12646361	100
Presentation	ISC 2024	12-16/05/2024 Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community	N/A	30
Participation in workshop	Parallel IO NHR workshop	07-08/05/2024 Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community	https://zenodo.org/records/12635997	25
Presentation	Digital Ocean Forum	13/06/2024 Brussels (Belgium)	Scientific community	Not uploaded yet	40
[Participation to a workshop]	1st Industry workshop	12/06/2024 Remote	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/12633780	25
[Organisation of a training event]	GPU Optimization with Kernel Tuner	12 - 13/09/2024 Remote	[HPC community]	N/A	30

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[Participation to a conference (POSTER)]	European Meteorological Society Annual Meeting	2-6/09/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14033989	1000
[Organisation of an outreach event]	European Meteorological Society Annual Meeting - side event	04/09/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	[General public]	N/A	60
[Organisation of a workshop]	Workshop on Advancements of Global Challenges Applications (PPAM2024)	8-11/09/2024 Ostrava (Czech Republic)	[Earth System Modelling community]	N/A	N/A
[Participation to a webinar]	"Storms, Eerie and Science" hour - EERIE, WarmWorld and nextGEMS	16/09/2024 Remote	[Earth System Modelling community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14033416	
[Participation to a workshop]	"Manual and Automated Vectorisation for the Integrated Forecasting System", EUPEX Forum	10/10/2024 Barcelona (Spain)	[Scientific community]	N/A	40
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	HPC User Forum	22/10/2014 Barcelona (Spain)	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14034167	N/A
[Participation to a workshop]	EuroHPC JU User Day	22/10/2024 Amsterdam (Netherlands)	[HPC community]	N/A	50
[Video/film]	SuperComputing24	17-22/11/2024 Atlanta (USA)	[HPC community]	N/A	N/A
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	OpenIFS User Meeting	13-15/05/2024 Remote	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14095029	20
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	National Hydrological and Climate Modeling Seminar	20/11/2024 Helsinki (Finland)	[Earth System Modelling community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14191942	50
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	Hidalgo2 - Hackathon on Atmosphere-Fire interaction	2/12/2024 Madrid (Online)	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14265300	N/A
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	Workshop ChEEse	10/12/2024	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14384651	50
[Organisation of a workshop]	HiPEAC Workshop day 1	20/1/2025 Barcelona	[HPC community]	N/A	40

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[Organisation of a workshop]	HiPEAC Workshop day 2	22/1/2025 Barcelona	[HPC community]	N/A	40
[Flyers/roll-up/slidedecks]	HiPEAC Booth	22/01/2025 Barcelona	[HPC community]	N/A	250
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/CoEs]	HiPEAC25 Round table	20/01/2025 Barcelona	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/14761971	35
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	AMS - 11th Symposium on High Performance Computing for Weather, Water, and Climate - HPCW: the High Performance Climate and Weather Benchmark Suite	16/01/2025, New Orleans	[HPC community]	N/A	7000
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/CoEs]	CASTIEL 2 Code of the Month	19/02/2025 Online	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15024552	20
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	E-Science Days	12.- 14.03.2025 Heidelberg (Germany)	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15175886	100
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	EGU 25	30.04.2025 Vienna	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15360450	40
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	EGU 25	02.05.2025 Vienna	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15363622	40
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	EGU 25	02.05.2025 Vienna	[Scientific community]	N/A	40
[Participation to a conference (POSTER)]	EGU25	01.05.2025 Vienna	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15401734	50
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	EGU25	30.04.2025 Vienna	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15487223	50
[Organisation of a conference]	EGU25, Session on Compression	01.05.2025 Vienna	[Scientific community]	N/A	100
[Participation to a webinar]	CONTINENTS webinar	28.05.2025 Online	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15537700	10
[Participation to a scientific event other]	EuroHPC Summit	18.03.2025 Krakov (Poland)	[HPC community]	N/A	60

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than a conference or workshop]					
[Participation to a conference (POSTER)]	EuroHPC Summit (poster)	18.03.2025 Krakov (Poland)	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15308546	1000
[Organisation of an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/Codes]	Training Code performance analysis with Extrae and Paraver	27.01.2025 Online	[HPC community]	N/A	40
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/Codes]	NCC Cyprus talk	25.06.2025 Online	[HPC community]	N/A	40
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/Codes]	CASTIEL 2 Code of the Month	19.02.2025 Online	[HPC community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15024552	50
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/Codes]	2025 Inpex Workshop	14/04/2025 Tokyo (Japan)	[HPC community]	N/A	50
[Participation to a scientific event other than a conference or workshop]	Kick-off meeting GANANA	07/05/2025 Remote	[HPC community]	N/A	N/A
[Participation to a scientific event other than a conference or workshop]	BSC Earth Science Department Seminars	20/05/2025 Remote	[Scientific community]	N/A	30
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/Codes]	CONTINENTS webinar	28/05/2025 Online	[HPC community]	N/A	10
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/Codes]	SPHERIC25	17/06/2025 Presential	[HPC community]	N/A	N/A
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	Hanami Workshop + Kokkos Training	13/01/2025 Barcelona	[HPC community]	N/A	50
[Participation to a workshop]	ISC 25 - Readiness of HPC Extreme-scale Applications Workshop	09-13/06/2025 Hamburg (Germany)	[HPC community]	N/A	4000

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[Participation to a workshop]	ISC 25 - Talk at the EuroHPC at Booth	09-13/062025 Hamburg (Germany)	[HPC community]	N/A	4000
[Participation to a workshop]	MAQAO - Workshop	06/03/2025 Rennes	[Scientific community]	N/A	15
[Participation to a workshop]	AMS 105th Annual Meeting, Collaborations for the exploration of the use of GPU accelerated computing for Weather and Climate community	16/01/2025 New Orleans (USA)	[Earth System Modelling community]	N/A	N/A
[Participation to a workshop]	EGU25 -	2704-0205/2025 Vienna	[Earth System Modelling community]	N/A	N/A
[Organisation of a workshop]	FDO Operations Workshop	11/06/2025 Online	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/15926971	20
[Participation to a conference (POSTER)]	CoRDI 2025	26-28/08/2025, Aachen	[Scientific community]	https://zenodo.org/records/16736202	100
[Participation to an event organised jointly with other initiatives/projects/CoEs]	EuroHPC Users Day	Copenhaguen 30 Sep-1 Oct	[Scientific community]	N/A	250
[Participation to a conference (TALK)]	2nd Workshop on Correctness and Reproducibility for Earth System Software	05-07/11/2025, Boulder, CO (virtual participation)	[Earth System Modelling community]	https://zenodo.org/records/17556219	30
[Organisation of a workshop]	FDO F2F Meeting	22-23.10.2025, Hamburg	[Scientific community]	N/A	10
[Participation to a workshop]	FDO F2F Meeting	27.-28.05.2025, Göttingen	[Scientific community]	NA	10

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

Type of the publication	Title of publication	Authors	Title of journal or equivalent	Volume, Number, pages	Year	Status (in preparation, submitted, published)	Peer-reviewed (Y/N)	Open access (Y/N)
[Article in journal]	Computing the ecRa radiation scheme with half-precision arithmetic	Anton Pershin, Matthew Chantry, Peter Domini Dueben, Robin J Hogan, Tim Palmer	ESS Open Archive	-	2023	Submitted / Preprint	N	Y
[Article in journal]	Deep learning for quality control of surface physiographic fields using satellite Earth observations	Tom Kimpson, Margarita Choulga, Matthew Chantry, Gianpaolo Balsamo, Souhail Boussetta, Peter Dueben, and Tim Palmer	EGU Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	27, 4661–4685	2023	Published	Y	Y
[Article in journal]	Improving Medium-Range Ensemble Weather Forecasts with Hierarchical Ensemble Transformers	Zied Ben Bouallègue, Jonathan A. Weyn, Mariana C. A. Clare, Jesper Dramsch, Peter Dueben, and Matthew Chantry	AMS Artificial Intelligence for the Earth Systems	3, 1	2024	Published	Y	Y
[Article in journal]	The computational and energy cost of simulation and storage for climate science: lessons from CMIP6	Mario C. Acosta ¹ , Sergi Palomas ¹ , Stella V. Paronuzzi Ticco ¹ , Gladys Utrera ¹ , Joachim Biercamp ² , Pierre-Antoine Bretonniere ¹ , Reinhard Budich ³ , Miguel Castrillo ¹ , Arnaud Caubel ⁴ , Francisco Doblas-Reyes ^{1,14} , Italo Epicoco ⁵ , Uwe Fladrich ⁶ , Sylvie Joussaume ⁴ , Alok Kumar Gupta ⁷ , Bryan Lawrence ⁸ , Philippe L. Sager ⁹ , Grenville Lister ⁸ , Marie-Pierre Moine ¹⁰ , Jean-Christophe Rioual ¹¹ , Sophie Valcke ¹⁰ , Niki Zadeh ¹² , and Venkatramani Balaji ¹³	Geoscientific Model Development	17, 3081–309	2024	Published	Y	Y
[Other]	Eviden's Center for Excellence in	-	InsideHPC	-	2024	Published	N	Y

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	Performance Programming (CEPP – Accelerate Workloads, Add Value to Simulation!							
[Publication in conference proceedings/workshop]	Bringing Auto-Tuning to HIP: Analysis of Tuning Impact and Difficulty on AMD and Nvidia GPUs	Milo Lurati, Stijn Heldens, Alessio Sclocco, Ben van Werkhoven	Euro-Par 2024: Parallel Processing	Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 14801.	2024	Published	Y	N
[Publication in conference proceedings/workshop]	Improving the Findability of Digital Objects in Climate Science by Adopting the FDO Concept	Marco Kulüke, Karsten Peters-von Gehlen, Ivonne Anders	Open Conference Proceedings, Vol 5 (2024): International FAIR Digital Objects Implementation Summit 2024	5	2025	published	Y	Y
[Publication in conference proceedings/workshop]	Centre of Excellence workshops at HIPEAC 2025 shift the needle in gender balance	Maria Arista-Romero, Rosa Rodriguez-Gaser, Marta García	HIPEAC info futures	June	2025	Published		
[Publication in conference proceedings/workshop]	Kernel Tuner: An open-source tool for optimizing GPU applications	Ben van Werkhoven	HIPEAC info futures	June	2025	Published		
[Article in journal]	Efficient variable precision reduction in chaotic climate models: Analysis of the NEMO case in the destination earth project	Stella V. Paronuzzi-Ticco, Gladys Utrera, Mario C. Acosta	Computers & Geosciences	November	2025	Published	Y	Y
[Publication in conference proceedings/workshop]	Centre of Excellence workshops at HIPEAC 2025 shift the needle in gender balance	Maria Arista-Romero, Rosa Rodriguez-Gaser, Marta García	HIPEAC Blog	August	2025	Published		

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

An Intellectual Property Management Plan for the whole ESiWACE3 project is given as Annex1

APPENDIX 1: Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Appendix 1: Intellectual Property Management Plan of D6.3 is an output of Task 6.5 (Exploitation and sustainability of project results) and is part of a series of complementary documents that track the intellectual property (IP) developed within the project and its potential use beyond it.

After D6.2 Appendix 1. Intellectual Property Management Plan (IPMP), where the strategy to maximise the exploitation of Results was defined, the initial IP portfolio was presented, among other things. D6.3 keeps tracking the evolution of the Results and their potential for exploitation.

INTRODUCTION

ESiWACE3 is a collaborative project including partners from industry and Research and Technology Organisations (RTO) that pursue the same objective but follow different strategies to exploit their Results. In addition to the different nature of the partners, different types of Results are expected from ESiWACE3, with different impact or level of exploitation. However, still with a common goal, to advance European HPC technologies and contribute to building a resilient European HPC ecosystem.

To maximise the use of the Results generated during the project, beyond it, a strategy to manage innovation has been defined in deliverables D6.1 and D6.2. The current deliverable appendix (D6.3), complement previous deliverable appendix D6.2 and reflects the progress of the activities outlined in Task 6.5.

According to the strategy defined, the Innovation Manager (IM) coordinates partners' efforts engaged in exploitation-related activities, defines guidelines for the management of the assets developed by the project (including knowledge and know-how) and prepares supporting material (i.e. templates) to facilitate the implementation of exploitation activities.

D6.3 Appendix is framed in Phase 3 with focus on monitoring and updating the Results, while going into detail in other aspects such as target market, Unique Value Proposition (UVP) and SWOT analysis.

ACTION PLAN - METHODOLOGY

The applied methodology and definitions have been introduced in D6.2 Appendix 1. This section aims to help the reader to get an overview of the main ideas, but for detailed information, please check appendix 1 in D6.2. A summary of these ideas is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the applied methodology

For a more effective communication between partners engaged in exploitation activities, a specific exploitation working group has been set up, including a main contact and a backup contact from each result. The IM (Innovation Manager) is the responsible to promote the working group and meetings.

To identify and monitor the Results developed within the project, the IM provided templates to the partners. For Period 2 (previous period), the template consisted of an excel document including

four different tabs addressing summary, preliminary data collection, IP traceability and definitions. The information collected during Period 2 has been extended in this document considering the updates of the results and additional information from the in-depth exploitation template for Period 3 (period reported in this document). For the latter, the template consists of a word document addressing issues such as market and target audience, identification of the Unique Value Proposition and SWOT analysis. Information has also been added about where the results can be found.

IP PORTFOLIO

The main objective of the ESiWACE3’s IP portfolio is to gather and present potential exploitable Results produced within the project, identify their ownership, the strategy for protecting the IP and the strategy for their exploitation. The ESiWACE3’s IP portfolio also aims to identify any possible issue regarding IP conflicts that could prevent the use of the Result outside the project. Compared to the previous deliverable Appendix 1 (D6.2), the IP portfolio main structure has been maintained, and additional fields have been added to include updates from Phase 2 (ex. where the result in published). These new fields help to monitor the results and see their evolution within the reporting period (M33).

Table 1: Example of updated fields in the IP tables

1	Result name						Result/KER
	Type	X	TRL	Expected	X	Ownership	X
				Current	X		
	IP	Traceability	X				
		Protection	X				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• X				
		Route/s	• X				
	Current status (M18) of the Result				X		
	Related projects				X		
	Where the result is published	X					
	Repository link	X					

Additionally, the complementary information collected during Phase 3 has been attached to this table, when it is related to the individual Result. The first row of the table summarises the Results included in the description. An example is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Example of table for complementary information (phase 3)

Result or results considered:			RXX- XX		
Market and target audience					
Sector/s of application	X				
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	X				
Potential competitors	X				
Competitive products	X				
Type of Market (select one)	Direct				
	Indirect				
	No market oriented				
Estimated MRL	X	Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When: X
				No →	Why: X
Main barriers to reach the market	X				
Unique Value Proposition					

What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	X
Which pains is your result solving?	X
Which gains is your result providing?	X
SWOT analysis	
Strengths	X
Opportunities	X
Weaknesses	X
Threats/ Risks	X

The complementary information collected from Phase 3 aims to give an overview of the market and target audience, the UVP offered by the Result, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. It is relevant to note that the nature of some ESiWACE3 Results may differ from the common understanding of product and market. These Results, namely those that will be released as open source in collaborative hubs (i.e. GitHub, GitLab) and that initially will not generate any monetary revenue but could indirectly lead to the creation of other business based on support, maintenance, or new products that don't need to be directly related with the partner, are considered products. Following the same approach, the open source "community" could be considered as an "indirect market", but still a market. For this reason, three different options have been considered for the type of market: a) Direct market, considering the common understanding of monetising the product and getting revenue from it; b) Indirect market, considering alternative "markets" that could indirectly lead to other business such as support, maintenance, or new products that don't need to be directly related with the partner neither return direct revenue (i.e. open source release) and; c) Not market oriented.

Besides the compilation and follow-up of the Results declared by the partners during the current period (M37), this section also compiles the background updates, if there were.

As part of a continuous monitoring, the information here presented will be updated, according to the evolution of the project, in D6.5 – Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan due in M47.

This section has been divided in the following two sub-sections, background updates and Results, being the latter structured as follows:

- First, a table summarising all Result, the owner, its classification and potential as KER is presented (subsection 5.2.1).
- Secondly, the Results are presented by partner with an initial table summarizing the Results generated by the partner and then individual tables showing the information of the corresponding Result (subsection 5.2.2). The complementary information from Phase 3 is also included in this section. This section presents the results with a single owner first, followed by those with more than one owner.

Background updates

No updates were declared during the current period.

Results

Summary of results

The updated summary of the Results presented in the appendix 1 to deliverable D6.2 above is shown in Table 3. This summary identifies the Result, the owner, its classification and potential as KER. In the table, the names of the results have a direct link to the tables with the details of each result to facilitate direct access to it. As the project advances, and following the pyramidal approach introduced in the methodology, the number of results with high potential for exploitation decrease. This can be because when going deeper into details, it makes more sense to consider some results as a whole or because, even being a result, as defined according to the CA, their potential to become a Key Exploitable Result (KER) is not as high as others.

Table 3. ESiWACE3 results summary

Nº	Result	Owner	Classification	Potential
R1	HCPW	ATOS, DKRZ	SW	KER
R2	AUTO-RPE	BSC	SW	KER
R3	Automatic Performance Profiling (APP)	BSC	SW	KER
R4	HPCW Risc-V version	BSC	SW	RESULT
R6	NEMO on GPU	NEMO Consortium (CMCC)	SW	KER
R7	Ophidia accessing Zarr format PSyclone	CMCC	SW	RESULT
R8	PSyclone	PSyclone partners (CSC)	SW	KER
R9	Summer School 2024	CSC, ATOS, DKRZ, JSC, UH, (WarmWorld)	Training material	RESULT
R10	Summer School 2025	CSC, ATOS, DKRZ, JSC, UH, (WarmWorld)	Training material	RESULT
R11	FDO4Climate: Initial Evaluation	DKRZ	Documentation	KER
R12	ICON-HPCW	DKRZ, MPI	SW	RESULT
R13	Field Compression Library	ECMWF, UH	SW	KER
R14	FVM	ECMWF	SW	KER
R15	Software Stack	JSC, ATOS, BSC, CSC	Documentation	RESULT
R16	Training Calendar	JSC	Documentation	RESULT
R17	Efficient data layouts for ESM output	MPI-M, DKRZ, BSC, ECMWF	Methodology	RESULT
R18	Energy-Efficient GPU Computing SC23 tutorial	NLESC	Methodology	RESULT
R19	ESiWACE3 Service 1	BSC, DKRZ, NLESC, ATOS	SW	RESULT
R22	Porting Integration EC-Earth4	EC-Earth Consortium	SW	RESULT
R23	Service catalogue	WP4 partners	Documentation	RESULT
R24	Containerization of EC-Earth	BSC, SMHI	Documentation	KER
R25	Docker EC-EARTH	BSC, SMHI	SW	KER
R26	Cartopy-Pyodide	UH	SW	RESULT
R27	Compression-Hackathon	UH, NLESC	SW	KER
R28	Field Compression Benchmark Suite	UH	SW	KER
R29	NetCDF-Pyodide	UH	SW	RESULT

R30	Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology	UH	SW	KER
R31	Compression Laboratory	UH, ECMWF	SW	KER
R32	Kernel Tuner Ecosystem	NLESC	SW	KER

Results by partner

This section compiles the updates Results declared by the partners during the current reporting period (M37). This preliminary information will be updated and complemented progressively in each corresponding deliverable (D6.5 in M47). The main objective of this preliminary IP portfolio is to gather and present the Results produced within the project, identify their ownership, the strategy for protecting the IP and the strategy for exploitation. Note that the strategy for exploitation is focused on individual Results, and not addressing or mentioning possible agreements reached, or under discussion, between partners. In addition, the IP portfolio will consider IP traceability to identify any possible issue that could prevent the use of the Result outside the project, will reflect the status of the Result during the reporting period, including as well the “current TRL” and the expected TRL at the end of the project.

For this deliverable, an update of the first identification of results has been carried out. A bottom-up approach is applied. Therefore, the present deliverable will focus on the identification of the Results and KER. The identification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was carried out jointly with all partners. Initially, each partner assessed whether their result had high potential (D6.2), and based on this classification, a workshop was held in November 2024 where partners could discuss and jointly evaluate which results could be considered KPIs. The final decision was made after reflection and consolidation of ideas following the workshop.

The Results are presented by partners in Tables 5 ff, according to the following structure. An initial table summarises the Results generated by the partner, and then individual tables show the information of the corresponding Result with multiple owners.

Individual results

ATOS

ATOS has not generated any individual results for the moment.
 ATOS has declared joint results.

BSC

Table 4. BSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R2	AUTO-RPE	Tool designed to help with the optimization of the numerical precision of computational science models written in Fortran.	KER	2
R3	Automatic Performance Profiling (APP)	Tool to automatically analyse the computational performance and generate reports of climate models.	KER	2
R4	HPCW Risc-V version	Ported version to RISC-V Linux of the HPCW suite	Result	1

R2	AUTO-RPE						KER
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	BSC
				Current	4		
	IP	Traceability	Open source. IP dependencies preventing its use outside the project have not been identified.				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Provider • Licensing - Open Source - Permissive (i.e. Apache, MIT ...) • Other 				
	Current status (M37) of the Result				Portability improved		
	Related projects				The result will potentially contribute to Destination Earth, EERIE, EDITO projects.		
	Where the result is published				Public repository		
Repository link				https://earth.bsc.es/gitlab/ces/hpc-for-es-team/AutoRPE			

Result or results considered:		R2 - AUTO-RPE	
Market and target audience			
Sector/s of application	Model developers		
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	Researchers who develop simulation programs with FORTRAM		
Potential competitors			
Competitive products			
Type of Market (select one)	Direct		
	Indirect		X
	No market oriented		
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When: 2024 published
		No →	Why:

Main barriers to reach the market	Steep learning curve
Unique Value Proposition	
What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	It provides an automatic adjustment of the numerical accuracy. You don't need an expert in the scientific field of the model
Which pains is your result solving?	It removes the need to have an expert in the scientific field of what the model is about.
Which gains is your result providing?	Improved computational performance
SWOT analysis	
Strengths	- Enables mixed-precision configurations that reduce memory and computational demands - Automates code modifications in Fortran, greatly reducing manual effort for legacy or large-scale scientific codes.
Opportunities	- Potential applicability in scientific fields beyond weather and climate. - Modern hardware allows shorter data types and there's a lack of tools to exploit them.
Weaknesses	- Limited to Fortran, resulting in a narrower user base. - Steep learning curve.
Threats/ Risks	- Maintainability challenges. - Limited resources for ongoing development.

R3	APP						KER
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	BSC
				Current	5		
	IP	Traceability	Third party dependences: Python packages, Autosubmit, BSC tools, OSU, STREAM, Latex (all open source)				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating and providing a service 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Provider Licensing - Open Source - Permissive (i.e. Apache, MIT ...) Other 				
	Current status (M37) of the Result				Proof of concept		
Related projects				The results will potentially contribute to EC-Earth related projects, Monarch related projects, TerraDT, DestinE.			
Where the result is published				Public repository			
Repository link				https://earth.bsc.es/gitlab/ces/hpc-for-es-team/automatic_performance_profiling			

R4	HPCW Risc-V version						Result
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	BSC
				Current	3		
	IP	Traceability	Dependences with LLVM toolchain and RISC-V Linux components under open-source licence and HPCW component licences				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative Research 				
	Current status (M37) of the Result				Establishing the required technology to execute the result		

Related projects	This result come from ESIWACE2 (HPWC), EPI SGA1 + EPI SGA2 and EUPILLOT (LLVM components), and will potentially contribute to other projects.
Where the result is published	Public repository but no open for the moment. Still in active development
Repository link	https://gitlab.bsc.es/rferrer/esiwace-hpcw-riscv

Result or results considered:		R4 - HPCW RISC-V version	
Market and target audience			
Sector/s of application	Industrial (as it is a benchmark and can be used to assess RISC-V systems suitability for HPC), Research (useful to evaluate in adaptation to new technologies)		
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	RISC-V system vendors, researchers working on RISC-V		
Potential competitors	Other well-established benchmarks such as SPEC.		
Competitive products	SPECHEPC		
Type of Market	Direct		
	Indirect		
	No market oriented		X
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes → No →	When: - Why: -
Main barriers to reach the market	-		
Unique Value Proposition			
What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	Existing system benchmarks may be too generic when willing to assess specific workloads for specific platforms. Porting HPCW to RISC-V makes a specialised benchmark for the RISC-V emerging architecture which due to its nature also includes HPC system vendors which will want to assess and market the efficiency of their systems running climate & weather benchmarks.		
Which pains is your result solving?	Uncertainty about the suitability of a RISC-V HPC system for climate & weather workloads.		
Which gains is your result providing?	Being able to assess how a RISC-V HPC system compares to other HPC systems (RISC-V or not) when running climate and weather applications.		
SWOT analysis			
Strengths	These are well established applications in the climate & weather space.		
Opportunities	RISC-V is a new ISA and so offerings in HPC need to assess their value.		
Weaknesses	RISC-V HPC systems are still in their infancy so this work may be too early.		
Threats/ Risks	Other similar benchmarks from more well established benchmark providers.		

CMCC -----

Table 5. CMCC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
	RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP
R6	NEMO on GPU	NEMO porting and integration on MN5 and LUMI	KER	2
R7	Ophidia accessing Zarr format	Prototype extension of Ophidia HPDA framework for supporting Zarr data format. This will allow applying data analytics on a data format which is gaining more traction in the community	Result	3
R8	PSyclone	Use of PSyclone in the NEMO build system.	KER	2

R6	NEMO on GPU						KER
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	CMCC	
			Current	3			
IP	Traceability	Dependences on Psyclone and XIOS					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and marketing a product or process • Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 					
Current status (M37) of the Result			proof of concept				
Related projects			The result will potentially contribute to other projects (TBD)				
Where the result is published			Public repository but no open for the moment. Still in development phase				
Repository link			https://forge.nemo-ocean.eu/nemo/nemo				

R7	Ophidia accessing Zarr format						Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	CMCC	
			Current	4			
IP	Traceability	Several dependencies on open-source libraries/tools, starting from NetCDF NCZarr					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 					
Current status (M37) of the Result			Integration completed and tested on different HPC systems (DKRZ, CSC, CMCC). Performance evaluation of the extensions with respect to different datasets planned.				
Related projects			The Ophidia components have been supported by multiple projects. The result will potentially contribute to other projects (TBD)				
Where the result is published			This has been released as part of Ophidia version 1.9.				
Repository link			The support is available at: https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-analytics-framework/ and https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/ophidia-io-server/				

R8	PSyclone						KER
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	CMCC	
			Current	4			
IP	Traceability	Based on open-source license					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 					
Current status (M37) of the Result			Integration of the PSyclone to compile GPU-enabled version of NEMO for Med24 and GLOB16 configuration				
Related projects			The PSyclone components have been supported by				

		multiple projects. The result will potentially contribute to other projects (TBD).
	Where the result is published	Public repository but no open for the moment. Still in progress.
	Repository link	https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone

CSC

CSC has not generated any individual results for the moment.
CSC has declared joint results.

DKRZ

Table 6. DKRZ – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS					
RESULT		Brief description		Classification	WP
R11	FDO4Climate: Initial Evaluation	Evaluation of the readiness of published climate simulation output for automated analysis.		KER	3

R11	FDO4Climate: Initial Evaluation					KER	
	Type	SCI	TRL	Expected	4	Ownership	DKRZ
				Current	4		
	IP	Traceability		Own background			
		Protection		Copyright			
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization activities Licensing - Open Source - Permissive Collaborative Research Participation in relevant forums/ standardization groups, etc. 			
		Route/s					
	Current status (M37) of the Result				Milestone M3.1 finished, the result was the topic of that milestone. Current work continues along the recommendations laid out in M3.1.		
Related projects				The result will potentially contribute to other projects (TBD).			
Where the result is published				Public repository but no open for the moment. Ongoing development			
Repository link				https://gitlab.dkrz.de/data-infrastructure-services/fdo			

Result or results considered			R11 - FDO4Climate: Initial Evaluation		
Market and target audience					
Sector/s of application	Quaternary sector (Research and Development, Information Technology, Education, Consulting Services)				
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	Generally, everyone relies on climate data for conducting their work (scientist, consultants, government advisors, among others)				
Potential competitors	None				
Competitive products	Advanced AI products (not known until today)				
Type of Market (select one)	Direct				
	Indirect		X		
	No market oriented				
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When: 2026		
		No →	Why:		

Main barriers to reach the market	Acceptance by global and interdisciplinary community
Unique Value Proposition	
What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	The implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Digital Objects (FDOs) enhances climate data management by improving data findability and interoperability. We develop tools to enable the adoption of the FDO concept for climate-science related data, e.g. large-volume climate model output. Eventually, this will lead to significantly more efficient analysis possibilities across disciplines. No similar work is done in the weather and climate realm now.
Which pains is your result solving?	Data wrangling due to incompatible data standards across disciplines, as well as subdisciplines in weather and climate science
Which gains is your result providing?	Increased FAIRness of computationally expensive climate data
SWOT analysis	
Strengths	Builds on existing and accepted community standards, transparent development process
Opportunities	Contribution to unified global data space
Weaknesses	Slow development process, due to many communities involved
Threats/ Risks	No acceptance by communities, difficult communication between disciplines

ECMWF -----

Table 7. ECMWF – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R14	FVM	New dynamical core of ECMWF that will be used for operational weather predictions and climate simulations.	KER	2

R14	FVM					KER	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	ECMWF
				Current	6		
	IP	Traceability		GT4Py (Open Source)			
		Protection		Copyright			
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s		• Further Research activities			
		Route/s		• Collaborative Research			
	Current status (M37) of the Result			Development in progress			
Related projects			The result will potentially contribute to other projects (TBD).				
Where the result is published			Public repository but no open for the moment. Still in progress.				
Repository link			-				

JSC -----

Table 8. JSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description	Classification	WP

R16	Training Calendar	Collecting and publishing domain-specific activities such as ESM user forums, workshops, and summer schools on topics of computational and data sciences as well as high performance computing	Result	5
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R16	Training Calendar					Result
	Type	EVENT	TRL	Expected Current	N/A N/A	Ownership JSC
	IP	Traceability	Own background			
		Protection	Copyright			
	Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	• Creating and providing a service		
			Route/s	• Education/ Training activities		
	Current status (M37) of the Result			Online training calendar has been created and integrated in ESIWACE web site		
	Related projects			Non		
Where the result is published			ESIWACE3 page web			
Repository link			https://www.esiwace.eu/training/trainings			

LT

LT has not generated any individual results for the moment.
 LT contributes mostly to actions to maximise impact. Not expected to generate any significant results.

MPI-M

MPI-M has not generated any individual results for the moment.
 MPI-M has declared joint results.

NLESC

Table 9. NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R18	Energy-Efficient GPU Computing SC23 tutorial	Training researchers and practitioners how to use improve the energy efficiency of their GPU applications. Demonstrating how to use Kernel Tuner and Kernel Float to this end.	Result	2&4
R32	Kernel Tuner Ecosystem	The Kernel Tuner Ecosystem is a set of tools and libraries to improve the performance of GPU software.	KER	1

R18	Energy-Efficient GPU Computing SC23 tutorial					Result
	Type	METH	TRL	Expected Current	N/A N/A	Ownership NLESC
	IP	Traceability	No dependences			

	Protection	Copyright
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Further Research activities
	Route/s	• Licensing - Open Source - Permissive
Current status (M37) of the Result		Material has been created and tutorial given at next SC.
Related projects		At the moment, there are no plans to use this result in other projects.
Where the result is published		-
Repository link		-

R32	Kernel Tuner Ecosystem					KER
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	NLESC
			Current	4		
IP	Traceability	No dependences				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Further Research activities				
	Route/s	• Licensing - Open Source - Permissive • Collaborative Research • Education/ Training activities				
Current status (M37) of the Result			Library has been created, currently being further tested and refined			
Related projects			This project will potentially contribute to other projects.			
Where the result is published			Public repository			
Repository link			https://github.com/KernelTuner			

Result or results considered:		R32 - Kernel Tuner Ecosystem	
Market and target audience			
Sector/s of application	High Performance Computing		
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	Developers of HPC applications		
Potential competitors	Kernel Tuning Toolkit (KTT) https://github.com/HiPerCoRe/KTT		
Competitive products	No commercial products		
Type of Market (select one)	Direct		
	Indirect		
	No market oriented		X
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When:
		No →	Why: research tool
Main barriers to reach the market	Core developers are all researchers, the tooling developed is open source and can also be used commercially		
Unique Value Proposition			
What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	Kernel Tuner: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports tuning all main GPU programming languages • Supports tuning for performance, energy efficiency, and other metrics • It does not add dependencies to the user's code 		
Which pains is your result solving?	Automating the process of tuning performance sensitive code.		
Which gains is your result providing?	Allows developers to improve the performance and energy efficiency of their program, and to make it performance portable.		
SWOT analysis			
Strengths	-		
Opportunities	-		
Weaknesses	-		

Threats/ Risks	-
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SMHI -----

SMHI has not generated any individual results for the moment.
 SMHI has declared joint results.

UH -----

Table 10. UH – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R26	Cartopy-Pyodide	Port Cartopy to work inside Pyodide and to contribute it to the Pyodide project such that Cartopy can now be used in Pyodide environments by anyone.	Result	3
R28	Field Compression Benchmark Suite	The field compression benchmark provides a highly scalable environment to benchmark and analyse the performance of different data compression methods on a large and diverse set of weather and climate datasets.	KER	3
R29	NetCDF-Pyodide	Our contribution is to port NetCDF to work inside Pyodide and to contribute it to the Pyodide project such that NetCDF can now be used in Pyodide environments by anyone.	Result	3
R30	Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology	The Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology provide a JupyterLab-like environment that has common climate and meteorology packages and libraries preinstalled.	KER	3

R26	Cartopy-Pyodide					Result	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	UH
				Current	6		
	IP	Traceability	Has dependences on Pyodide and Cartopy (Open Source)				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Creating and providing a service				
		Route/s	• Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft				
	Current status (M37) of the Result			Cartopy is now provided as an available-by-default package in Pyodide			
	Related projects			This project will potentially contribute to other projects.			
	Where the result is published			Public repository			
	Repository link			https://github.com/pyodide/pyodide/pull/3909			

R28	Field Compression Benchmark Suite					KER	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	5	Ownership	UH
				Current	4		
	IP	Traceability	Has dependences on Rust crates and Python packages (Open				

		Source)	
	Protection	Copyright	
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source – Permissive • Participation in relevant forums/ standardization groups, etc.
	Current status (M37) of the Result		Development of the benchmark suite has been paused since November 2023 due to parental leave and will resume once the Compression Hackathon paper has been submitted. At this time, the benchmark suite can benchmark the performance and goodness (via several metrics) across the variables and dimensions of a variety of datasets in NetCDF, Zarr, or GRIB format.
Related projects		This project will potentially contribute to other projects.	
Where the result is published		Ongoing development, will be published together with a scientific paper	
Repository link		-	

R29	NetCDF-Pyodide					Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	UH
			Current	6		
IP	Traceability	Has dependences on Pyodide and NetCDF4 (Open Source)				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M37) of the Result		NetCDF4 is now provided as an available-by-default package in Pyodide				
Related projects		This project will potentially contribute to other projects.				
Where the result is published		Public repository				
Repository link		https://github.com/pyodide/pyodide/pull/3910				

R30	Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology					KER
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	UH
			Current	5		
IP	Traceability	Has dependences on Pyodide and JupyterLite (Open Source)				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service • Further Research activities 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source – Copyleft • Education/ Training activities • Collaborative Research • Service Provider 				
Current status (M37) of the Result		Versions v0.1.0 and v0.2.0 of the online lab have been published and now provide support for more packages and applications beyond the online compression lab.				
Related projects		This project will potentially contribute to other projects.				
Where the result is published		Public repository				

Repository link	https://github.com/climet-eu/lab
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Joint and Multiple results

ATOS / DKRZ -----

Table 11. ATOS/DKRZ – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R1	HCPW	High Performance Climate and Weather benchmarking suite. HPCW isolates key elements in the workflow of weather and climate prediction systems to improve performance and to allow a detailed performance comparison for different hardware platforms thus fostering co-design with vendors and technology providers.	KER	1

R1	HCPW					KER	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	ATOS, DKRZ
				Current	6		
	IP	Traceability	Open-source licence components developed outside the project (ICON; IFS Dwarfs: ecTrans, ecRad, dwarf-p-cloudsc; NEMO) are used, agreements with the owners are in place.				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Further Research activities				
		Route/s	• Licensing - Open Source - Permissive				
	Current status (M37) of the Result			Development towards version 3 release			
	Related projects			ESCAPE-2, ESIWACE2 and potential others (EPI-SGA2, EMOPASS)			
	Where the result is published			Public repository but no open for the moment. Still no ranking, active development			
	Repository link			https://gitlab.dkrz.de/hpcw/hpcw/			

Result or results considered:		R1 - HPCW	
Market and target audience			
Sector/s of application	HPC		
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weather and climate supercomputing centres including general purpose supercomputing centres. HPC vendors & Technology providers 		
Potential competitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TOP500 		
Competitive products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HPL HPCG 		
Type of Market (select one)	Direct		
	Indirect		X
	No market oriented		
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When: -
		No →	Why: Open source (released in 2025)
Main barriers to reach the market	Technical adoption		
Unique Value Proposition			

What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	No existing comparable state of the art solution at this stage. HPCW is a domain specific benchmark dedicated to weather and climate domain. An initiative in the context of ECP (USA Exascale Computing Project) existed but is no longer maintained (E3SM-Kernels).
Which pains is your result solving?	Easy and quick deployment of reference benchmarks including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • source code, • reference test cases, • result validation, • performance metric extraction
Which gains is your result providing?	Ranking for supercomputers to run efficiently weather and climate flagship applications
SWOT analysis	
Strengths	Representative of the weather and climate needs (currently in Europe) Reference benchmark
Opportunities	Worldwide adoption (short term targets: Japan, India) Reach other scientific domains to create another domain specific benchmark
Weaknesses	Adoption improvement
Threats/ Risks	Needs might evolve faster than the benchmark components. New framework technologies for benchmarking

CSC / ATOS / DKRZ / JSC / UH -----

Table 12. CSC/ATOS/DKRZ/JSC/UH – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R9	Summer School 2024	Training of Early Career Scientists in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use the latest HPC environments	Result	5
R10	Summer School 2025	Training of Early Career Scientists in methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use the latest HPC environments	Result	5

R9	Summer School 2024					Result	
	Type	EVENT	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	CSC, ATOS, DKRZ, JSC,UH
				Current	N/A		
	IP	Traceability	Own background				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy		Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service • Education/ Training activities • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 			
			Route/s				
	Current status (M37) of the Result				Development of training material has begun		
Related projects				Possibility to contribute in AI4PEX			
Where the result is published				ESiWACE3 web page			
Repository link				https://www.esiwace.eu/training-event/#training-materials			

R10	Summer School 2025					Result	
	Type	EVENT	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	CSC, ATOS, DKRZ, JSC,UH
				Current	N/A		
IP	Traceability	Own background					

	Protection	Copyright
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and providing a service
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education/ Training activities • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft
Current status (M37) of the Result		Pending summer school 2024 to begin
Related projects		Possibility to contribute in AI4PEX
Where the result is published		ESiWACE3 web page
Repository link		https://www.esiwace.eu/training-event/#training-materials

DKRZ / MPI -----

Table 13. DKRZ/MPI – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R12	ICON-HPCW	This is the application of an existing code (the Climate and Weather Model ICON. NOT developed by ESiWACE3) within the HPCW Benchmark suite.	Result	1

R12	ICON-HPCW				Result		
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	8	Ownership	DKRZ, MPI
				Current	6		
IP	Traceability	ICON is co-developed by several institutions. It is open source and is being used as a component of the HPCW benchmark suite.					
	Protection	Copyright					
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 					
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Permissive (i.e. Apache, MIT ...) • Education/ Training activities 					
Current status (M37) of the Result			A version of ICON included into HPCW				
Related projects			This result come from other EU projects and will potentially contribute to HANAMI				
Where the result is published			Public repository but no open for the moment. It's a core component of HPCW that still no ranking, active development				
Repository link			https://gitlab.dkrz.de/hpcw/hpcw/				

Result or results considered:		R12 - ICON-HPCW	
Market and target audience			
Sector/s of application	Industrial, Research		
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	Technology providers, compute centres		
Potential competitors	-		
Competitive products	No other known climate-specific benchmark suite		
Type of Market (select one)	Direct		
	Indirect		X
	No market oriented		
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When: 2025
		No →	Why: -

Main barriers to reach the market	Only a component of HPCW, so tied to HPCW's properties
Unique Value Proposition	
What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	There is currently no benchmark suite tailored towards the needs of climate and weather science. Including a state-of-the-art climate model, such as ICON, into HPCW results in a benchmark suite that is able to accurately represent the computational and communication patterns of climate applications. Using ICON for this purpose instead of other applications is optimal due to previous experience with the model, the open-source license and the continued development of ICON, making sure that both HPCW and ICON itself stay relevant in the domain.
Which pains is your result solving?	Current benchmarks are not suited to properly judge a system's suitability for climate science. Including a climate science application in a benchmark remedies this problem.
Which gains is your result providing?	Accurate representation of computational and communication patterns of climate applications
SWOT analysis	
Strengths	Good representative for climate and weather applications.
Opportunities	Enabling simple porting of ICON to many different machines.
Weaknesses	Applications of this size are somewhat unwieldy.
Threats/ Risks	Requires maintenance to keep up to date, which requires personnel.

ECMWF / UH -----

Table 14. ECMWF/UH – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R13	Field Compression Library	It can be used by scientific groups to explore data compression for weather and climate science	KER	3

R13	Field Compression Library					KER	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	ECMWF/UH
				Current	6		
	IP	Traceability	Dependencies in Python packages, incl. Numcodecs (Open Source)				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and marketing a product or process • Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft (i.e. GPL) • Collaborative Research 				
	Current status (M37) of the Result				Development is ongoing, a prototype is used in the compression laboratory (R31). The library will likely be split into several modular Python packages to make them easier to (re)use for the broader community.		
Related projects				This result will potentially contribute to other projects.			
Where the result is published				ESiWACE web page			
Repository link				-			

JSC / ATOS / BSC / CSC -----

Table 14. JSC/ATOS/BSC/CSC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS			
RESULT	Brief description		Classification
R15	Software Stack	Review and consolidate the software stack for ESM applications	Result

R15	Software Stack					Result
	Type	PROD	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership
				Current	N/A	
IP	Traceability		It primarily comprises open-source components but needs third-party licensing for specific tools such as Intel compilers or model-specific packages.			
	Protection		Copyright			
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s		• Standardization activities			
	Route/s		• Service Provider			
Current status (M37) of the Result			Consolidated list of ESM software has been prepared			
Related projects			The stack builds upon knowledge and tools curated in previous projects such as ESiWACE1 and ESiWACE2 and integrates elements from the HPCW benchmark framework. This result will potentially contribute to other projects.			
Where the result is published			Public repository			
Repository link			https://gitlab.jsc.fz-juelich.de/zou1/software-list			

Result or results considered:		R15 - Software Stack	
Market and target audience			
Sector/s of application	Can be applied in climate and weather forecasting, energy and agriculture planning, environmental monitoring, disaster prediction, policy-making, and academic research, supporting risk assessment, resource management, and scientific advancements		
Potential costumers/ stakeholders	All model users at supercomputer centres		
Potential competitors	Proprietary climate tools, national and regional models, open-source frameworks like CESM, in-house solutions, and cloud-based platforms offering AI-driven modelling.		
Competitive products	Programme container		
Type of Market (select one)	Direct		
	Indirect		
	No market oriented		No
Planning to go to the market?	If	Yes →	When:
		No →	Why: research focus, open-source goals
Main barriers to reach the market	complexity of integration with existing systems and limited standardization across ESM frameworks.		
Unique Value Proposition			
What makes your result different and attractive compared to existing or State of the Art solutions?	The common software stack for ESM stands out with its broad compatibility, enabling seamless integration across diverse HPC systems. It emphasizes community-driven development, fostering collaboration and transparency, and is designed to be modular and scalable, ensuring adaptability for evolving research needs. Unlike many proprietary or niche solutions, it offers an open-source framework, maximizing accessibility and promoting innovation. By supporting cutting-edge HPC capabilities, it		

	ensures efficient performance and reproducibility, making it a future-proof choice for Earth system modelling advancements.
Which pains is your result solving?	It will simplify integration across diverse HPC systems, reducing the technical complexity of adapting to different environments.
Which gains is your result providing?	It allows users to easily tailor the stack to their specific research needs, ensuring it grows with evolving scientific requirements. By being community-driven, the software stack encourages collaboration across research institutions, leading to faster innovation and knowledge-sharing.
SWOT analysis	
Strengths	Compatibility with diverse HPC systems, ensures efficient performance. Community-driven development encourages innovation and continuous improvement.
Opportunities	Growing demand for climate and Earth system models offers a significant market for expanding usage. Collaborations with research institutions and public agencies can drive further development and adoption.
Weaknesses	Lack of commercial support may limit resources for fast troubleshooting and user support. Steep learning curve for new users unfamiliar with the software stack. Potential limitations in specialized functionalities compared to proprietary solutions.
Threats/ Risks	Technological changes and rapid advancements may require constant updates to maintain relevance. Potential funding instability for continued development, particularly if research priorities shift. Risk of fragmentation in the community if collaboration falters or competing solutions emerge.

MPI-M / BSC / DKRZ / ECMWF -----

Table 15. MPI-M/BSC/DKRZ /ECMWF – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT		Brief description	Classification	WP
R17	Efficient data layouts for ESM output	Data layouts for fast ingestion, cataloguing, distribution and retrieval	Result	3

R17	Efficient data layouts for ESM output				Result		
	Type	METH	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	MPI-M, BSC, DKRZ, ECMWF
				Current	5		
	IP	Traceability	Based on open source				
		Protection	Development in progress				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft • Licensing - Open Source - Permissive • Collaborative Research 				
Current status (M37) of the Result			Exploration of available concepts				
Related projects			This result come partially from WarmWorld and DestinE and will potentially contribute to other EU projects				
Where the result is published			Public repository				
Repository link			https://digital-earths-global-hackathon.github.io/catalog/				

NLESC / ATOS / BSC / DKRZ -----

Table 16. NLESC/ATOS/BSC/DKRZ/NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R19	ESiWACE3 Service 1	Service 1 creates small collaborative projects between ESiWACE3 partners and researcher in weather and climate to provide guidance, assistance, and training to help researchers with porting and optimizing their weather and climate simulations for modern HPC systems.	Result	4

R19	ESiWACE3 Service 1					Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	NLESC, ATOS, BSC, DKRZ
			Current	N/A		
IP	Traceability	Created with the knowledge of the partners involved				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Further Research activities				
	Route/s	• Collaborative Research				
Current status (M37) of the Result			Service has been created and is up and running			
Related projects			This result was created thanks to the knowledge acquired during previous EU projects.			
Where the result is published			Public repository			
Repository link			-			

SMHI / BSC / NLESC -----

Table 17. SMHI/BSC/NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R22	Porting Integration EC-Earth4	Porting/integration on LUMI, MN5 and national systems	Result	1

R22	Porting Integration EC-Earth4					Result
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	SMHI, BSC, NLeSC
			Current	5		
IP	Traceability	Based on open source				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Further Research activities				
	Route/s	• Collaborative Research				
Current status (M37) of the Result			The porting and integration have been completed in LUMI, ECMWF HPC2020, NSC (Freja and Tetralith) and on MN6			
Related projects			-OptimESM			
Where the result is published			-			
Repository link			-			

SMHI / ATOS / BSC / DKRZ / NLESC -----

Table 18. SMHI/ATOS/BSC/DKRZ/NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R23	Service catalogue	Collection of partner expertise and specific service offers for the public	Result	2

R23	Service catalogue					Result
Type	DOC	TRL	Expected	N/A	Ownership	SMHI, ATOS, BSC, DKRZ, NLESC
			Current	N/A		
IP	Traceability	Own background				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Creating and providing a service				
	Route/s	• Collaborative Research				
Current status (M37) of the Result			Published on ESiWACE3 website			
Related projects			N/A			
Where the result is published			-			
Repository link			-			

SMHI / ATOS / BSC / DKRZ / NLESC -----

Table 19. SMHI/ATOS/BSC/DKRZ/NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R24	Containerization of EC-Earth	Containerization of EC-Earth	KER	1

R24	Containerization of EC-Earth					KER
Type	DOC	TRL	Expected	6	Ownership	SMHI, BSC
			Current	5		
IP	Traceability	OpenMPI (BSD), FFTW (GPL), ecCodes (Apache), netCDF (BSD), HDF5 (BSD), Apptainer (BSD)				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	• Creating and providing a service				
	Route/s	• Licensing - Open source - Copyleft				
Current status (M37) of the Result			Done on SMHI HPC			
Related projects			TBD			
Where the result is published			Public repository but no open for the moment. pending publication.			
Repository link			-			

BSC / SMHI -----

Table 20. BSC/SMHI – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS							
RESULT		Brief description			Classification	WP	
R25	Docker EARTH	EC-	Containerization of the code EC-EARTH for running climate simulation			KER	1
R25	Docker EC-EARTH					KER	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	BSC, SMHI
				Current	5		
	IP	Traceability	EC-Earth is licensed software. Apptainer is open source				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating and marketing a product or process • Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Copyleft 				
Current status (M37) of the Result				In development			
Related projects				This result come from AUTOSUBMIT WF manager and EC-EARTH			
Where the result is published				Public repository but no open for the moment.			
Repository link				-			

UH / NLESC -----

Table 21. UH/NLESC – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS							
RESULT		Brief description			Classification	WP	
R27	Compression-Hackathon		This result could be used to drastically lower the storage and data transfer costs for model restart states. It is a result of the first ESiWACE3 Hackathon.			KER	3
R27	Compression-Hackathon					KER	
	Type	SW	TRL	Expected	3	Ownership	UH, NLESC
				Current	3		
	IP	Traceability	Dependencies on ZFP compressor				
		Protection	Copyright				
	Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 				
		Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source – Permissive • Collaborative Research 				
Current status (M37) of the Result				The results of the hackathon have been published. A subsequent research project, which significantly expanded the exploration of the model's state-loss compression, has been completed and a paper on it has been published.			
Related projects				This result will potentially contribute to other EU projects.			
Where the result is published				Public repository			
Repository link				https://zenodo.org/records/10209708			

UH / ECMWF -----

Table 22. UH/ECMWF – Summary of Results

SUMMARY of EW3 RESULTS				
RESULT	Brief description		Classification	WP
R31	Compression Laboratory	The (field) compression laboratory builds on ECMWF's field compression library. It provides several Jupyter notebooks that explore data compression for weather and climate data.	KER	3

R31	Compression Laboratory					KER
Type	SW	TRL	Expected	7	Ownership	UH, ECMWF
			Current	6		
IP	Traceability	Dependencies on Python packages (Open Source)				
	Protection	Copyright				
Expected Exploitation strategy	Path/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further Research activities 				
	Route/s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensing - Open Source - Permissive (i.e. Apache, MIT ...) • Education/ Training activities • Collaborative Research 				
Current status (M37) of the Result			Versions v0.1.0 and v0.2.0 of the compression lab notebooks have been released, which explore different compressors, data sources, and provide several example datasets.			
Related projects			This result will potentially contribute to other EU projects.			
Where the result is published			Public repository			
Repository link			https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks			

ANALYSIS

The IP management plan for EW3 and the corresponding guidelines for its implementation have been presented in this document. As part of the implementation, the updated version of the Results/IP portfolio has been also presented.

Up to 29 Results have been identified, of which 15 have been identified as KER due to their high potential to contribute to scientific advances. More of 80% of the Results will contribute to extend the open-source community including open-source hardware, and up to 20% will contribute to increase the HPC portfolio of the partners.

Also noteworthy are the relationships with other European projects. Almost all the results will contribute to future research activities stemming from the exchange of information, either by continuing a previous project within ESiWACE3 or by using ESiWACE3 results in other projects to further develop cutting-edge European technologies and promote international and interdisciplinary collaboration opportunities. For example, in ESiWACE3 you can find the continuation of developments from projects such as ESiWACE2, EPI SGA1 + EPI SGA2, EUPILLOT, ESCAPE-2, or Ophidia, among others. And some of the developments from ESiWACE3 have already been transferred or are planned to be transferred in the coming year, to projects such as EPI-SGA2,

EMOPASS, Destination Earth, EERIE, EDITO, EC-Earth related projects, Monarch related projects, TerraDT, AI4PEX, or HANAMI.

NEXT STEPS

As the project progresses and the results evolve, continuous monitoring will inform updates to subsequent deliverables. In accordance with the strategy defined in documents D6.1 and D6.2, and as part of the final (4th) phase, we will analyse the results further to identify their potential impact, the planned roadmap and their sustainability. Following the last workshop in November 2025, it was also decided to create a canvas to support the Exploitable Key Results (KERs) strategy. This work will be reflected in deliverable D6.5, on which our primary focus will be the Exploitable Key Results (KERs).

ABBREVIATIONS

A list of abbreviations:

Table 23. Abbreviations

Acronym	Explanation
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
ESiW3	ESiWACE3
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High Performance Computing
IM	Innovation Manager
IP	Intellectual Property
IPMP	Intellectual Property Management Plan
METH	Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)
PMO	Project Manager Office
PROD	Product (new or improved)
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SCI	Scientific discovery, model, theory, (...)
SW	Software
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UVP	Unique Value Proposition